

SCIENCE IDENTITY AND ACADEMIC SELF-EFFICACY OF JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract. This study examined the relationship between science identity and academic self-efficacy among junior high school students in Davao Oriental. Utilizing a quantitative-descriptive-correlational approach, the sample comprised 150 junior high school students who completed a survey. The findings revealed that the extent of science identity among the students was very high, indicating a solid identification and connection with the field of science. Additionally, the students exhibited high academic self-efficacy, suggesting a belief in their ability to succeed academically. Notably, the study also found a significant relationship between science identity and academic self-efficacy, indicating that students' confidence in their educational capabilities increased as they developed a stronger sense of identity in science. Specifically, science recognition emerged as the sole domain of science identity that significantly influenced academic self-efficacy, highlighting the importance of recognizing and valuing science-related achievements and contributions in fostering students' confidence and belief in their intellectual abilities. These findings contribute to our understanding of the factors that shape students' academic self-efficacy and emphasize the role of science identity in promoting academic confidence. The implications of these findings underscore the need for educational interventions and programs that foster science identity and recognize students' accomplishments in the science field. Educators can enhance students' academic self-efficacy and foster a positive attitude toward science education by cultivating a supportive and inclusive environment that promotes science recognition and identity development.

KEY WORDS

1. science identity 2. academic self-efficacy 3. Davao Oriental

1. Introduction

Despite the ongoing efforts of the Department of Education, the quality of science education in the Philippines remains a pressing concern. Many students struggle to develop a strong sense of science identity and academic self-efficacy. This situation not only hampers their interest in science-related careers but also poses a significant threat to the country's workforce and economic development. This study, conducted through a quantitative research design, aims to explore the factors influencing science identity and academic self-efficacy among Filipino junior high school students, a crucial step toward addressing this urgent issue. Historically, African American students have not experienced great success in science and are significantly underrepresented in science courses and science-related careers (Russell Atwater,

2005, as cited by White, DeCuir-Gunby, Kim, (2019). Understanding the development of science identity for students of color is essential because it helps construct a connection to the belief that science has value and that the student can successfully engage in the sciences (Flowers III Banda, 2016). The United States has been developing weak science identities and increased negative perceptions of science as a field of study, resulting in what is known as scientific pipeline leakage (Schultz et al., 2011). For example, the National Science Board (2016) showed that 17In the National research gaps, Insufficient STEM graduates exist in the Philippines; therefore, the country requires more scientists. (Anito, Morales Palisoc, 2019). Compared to the UNESCO recommendation of 380 per million, the Philippines only has 189 scientists per million people. (Anito et al., 2019). According to Rafanan and Rogayan (2020), the low number of scientists in the country can be primarily attributed to the low number of STEM graduates. In addition, they stated that the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) report disclosed that the STEM completion rate is only 21.10Although the Philippine government has implemented various policies and programs to improve the quality of science education, there still needs to be a persistent problem of low interest, motivation, and confidence among Filipino students in science-related subjects. This research gap is critical because science identity and academic self-efficacy are important factors affecting students' educational and career aspirations, significantly affecting the country's economic development. Understanding the factors contributing to this problematic situation is essential for developing effective interventions and programs to improve students' science identity and academic self-efficacy and promote a greater interest in science-related careers among Filipino youth. In the local settings, Likes in a study executed at the University of Mindanao-Panabo College by Allawan (2021) asserted that science education in the Philippines, especially in primary education, is lagging elsewhere in the world. Limited studies have been conducted in Davao Oriental that explore the science identity and academic self-efficacy of junior high school students, especially in a global health crisis that has disrupted the educational system. The current situation highlights the need to understand how these students perceive their capabilities in science education and how the pandemic has affected their academic self-efficacy. Thus, conducting research in this area can provide a deeper understanding of the situation of junior high school students in the province and inform education policymakers and stakeholders on how to address the issues they face. The research gap in science identity and academic self-efficacy lies in the need for further investigation into the complex interplay between these two constructs, particularly in diverse populations and across different educational levels. While existing studies have established their importance, a deeper understanding of how science identity and academic self-efficacy mutually influence each other could provide valuable insights for promoting STEM engagement and academic success. Despite the growing body of literature on science identity and academic self-efficacy, there is a significant research gap on the problematic situation of Filipino junior high school students' science identity and academic self-efficacy. The rationale for investigating Filipino junior high school students' science identity and academic self-efficacy stems from the urgency to address a significant educational challenge in the Philippines. As science education plays a pivotal role in the country's development, it is crucial to assist students in cultivating a strong sense of science identity and academic self-efficacy. The current situation poses a concern as many students lack interest in pursuing science-related careers, potentially hindering the nation's economic growth and competitiveness. Consequently, it becomes imperative to

explore various factors influencing science identity and academic self-efficacy among Filipino junior high school students, including socio-cultural context, classroom practices, and individual characteristics. By delving into this research gap, valuable insights can be gained to inform educational interventions and strategies tailored to the needs of Filipino students. Understanding the socio-cultural context surrounding science education in the Philippines would enable educators and policymakers to design inclusive and culturally relevant approaches that foster a positive science identity and enhance academic self-efficacy. Moreover, investigating the role of classroom practices, such as pedagogical methods and teacher-student interactions, could provide practical guidance for creating supportive learning environments that empower students to engage with science and develop confidence in their abilities. These factors include the socio-cultural context, classroom practices, and individual characteristics. This study's findings are expected to pave the way for developing effective interventions and programs that can enhance students' science identity and academic self-efficacy, thereby contributing to the overall improvement of science education in the Philippines.

2. Methodology

This chapter presents the methods and procedures the researcher will use to conduct the study. It covers the research design, research respondents, research locale, research instrument, ethical considerations, data gathering procedure, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—This study used a quantitative non-experimental research design utilizing descriptive correlation with regression analysis. Quantitative research involves collecting and analyzing numerical data (Skinner, 2020). One common type was a non-experimental study that consists of no manipulation of the variable, mainly independent. It covers various studies, including descriptive and correlational (Khaldi, 2017). A quantitative correlational design was appropriate for a study investigating the relationship between science identity and academic self-efficacy among junior high school students. This design was helpful because it allows the researcher to examine the relationship between two variables and determine whether a correlation exists and the strength and direction of that correlation. It also allows for statistical methods to analyze the data and test hypotheses, which is essential in determining the significance of the findings. This design is particularly relevant to the study as it focuses on understanding the relationship between two specific variables in a particular population. The study results could inform educational policies and practices that enhance junior high school students' science identity and academic self-efficacy, ultimately leading to improved academic performance and future career success.

2.2. Research Respondents—The researcher used a random sampling technique to identify this study's respondents. Random sampling is a part of the sampling technique in which each sample has an equal probability of being chosen (Meng, 2013). The following are the inclusion and exclusion criteria that the researcher observed, namely, male or female junior high school students from one of the public learning institutions in the Division of Davao Oriental, the school where the student is enrolled should be recognized by the Department of Education, and willing to give his or her consent for this study. A total of 150 students were catered to during this study. In research, 100 was considered the minimum

sample size when the population was identified as significant (Alshibly,2018).

2.3. *Research Instrument*—The study used a survey questionnaire as the instrument that was adapted and modified to fit the research objectives and the population being studied. A survey questionnaire was appropriate for this study as it allowed the researcher to quickly gather a large amount of data. Moreover, by adapting and modifying the survey questionnaire, the researcher could tailor the questions to be more relevant and specific to the research objectives and the population being studied. The questionnaire used for this study underwent validation by experts in the field of education. Afterward, it was pilot-tested to establish validity and reliability. This study utilized a 5-point Likert Scale in the survey questionnaire. A Likert Scale was a widely used measurement tool in social sciences, particularly in educational research, to measure individuals’ attitudes, opinions, and

perceptions on a particular subject. It allowed respondents to express their agreement or disagreement with a statement using a five-point scale ranging from strongly agree to disagree strongly. Using a 5-point Likert Scale in this study is appropriate as it provides a range of responses that could capture nuances in the respondents’ opinions or perceptions. The scale allows easy data analysis, as reactions can be easily tabulated and statistically analyzed. Using a standardized scale such as the 5-point Likert Scale also increases the reliability and validity of the data collected, as it allows for comparisons across different studies. For the independent variable, science identity, a modified and adapted Student Science Identity (SSI) questionnaire from the study of Chen and Wei (2020) was used. The questionnaire consists of 24 items. The Likert Scale below was used to assess the science identity of junior high school students.

Range, Descriptive Equivalent, and Descriptive Interpretation

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The scientific identity of the students is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The scientific identity of the students is very often manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The scientific identity of the students is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The scientific identity of the students is rarely manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The student’s science identity is never manifested.

A modified and adapted Academic Self-Efficacy Scale questionnaire from Dullas’s (2018) study was used for the dependent variable, academic self-efficacy. The questionnaire

consists of 62 items. The Likert scale below was used to assess the academic self-efficacy of junior high school students.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—These are the steps the researcher adhered to and exe-

cuted in the pre-and post-conduct of the study. They were adapting, Modifying, Validation, and

Range, Descriptive Equivalent, and Descriptive Interpretation

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The academic self-efficacy of students is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The academic self-efficacy of students is very often manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The academic self-efficacy of students is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The academic self-efficacy of students is rarely manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The academic self-efficacy of students is never manifested.

Pilot Testing the Survey Questionnaire. The researcher began by reviewing existing literature and research studies related to the topic to adjust and modify a survey questionnaire appropriate for the study. After adapting the survey, the researcher conducted a validation process by sending the crafted questionnaire to three education experts to ensure that the questions accurately measured the studied constructs. A pilot test was also conducted with a small sample of respondents to identify any problems or issues with the survey and to refine the questions accordingly. The researcher performed this from April 24 to April 30, 2023. They were asking for Permission to Conduct the Study. Before conducting the study, the researcher sought permission from the relevant authorities, including the Dean of the Graduate School at Rizal Memorial College and the Superintendent of the Department of Education Division of Davao Oriental. A detailed description of the study was provided, and the cooperation and support of these authorities were sought to contribute to the success of the research. The researcher performed this from May 1 to May 6, 2023. Administration and Retrieval of Informed Consent and Assent, Administration and Retrieval of Survey Ques-

tionnaire. Before administering the survey, the researcher provided respondents with a detailed explanation of the study, including the purpose, procedures, risks, and benefits, and obtained informed consent from adult respondents and assent from minors. Respondents were allowed to withdraw from the study without penalty. After obtaining consent, the survey questionnaire was administered to respondents, either online or in person, and all responses were kept confidential and anonymous. The researcher performed this from May 8 to May 13, 2023. Gathering and Tabulation of Data. After collecting all the surveys, the researcher gathered and tabulated the data. The responses were checked for completeness and accuracy and then entered into a database or statistical software for analysis. Appropriate statistical methods were used to analyze the data and test the hypotheses. The researcher performed this from May 15 to May 20, 2023. They were drawing Conclusions and Recommendations. Finally, the researcher drew conclusions based on the analysis's results and created recommendations for future research and practice. The data supported the findings and recommendations and were aligned with the research objectives. The study's limitations were considered, and areas for further investiga-

Extent of the Academic Self-Efficacy of Junior High School Students from Davao Oriental

Table 2 presents the calculated means and descriptive levels of the indicators of academic self-efficacy of junior high school students from Davao Oriental. The table includes four indicators: internal locus of control, competence, persistence, and self-regulated learning. For each indicator, the table reports the calculated mean and descriptive level, providing information about the overall level of the student's academic self-efficacy in science. The overall mean for academic self-efficacy of junior high school

The competence and persistence indicators both have a mean of 3.54, indicating that students feel confident in their ability to complete tasks and persist in the face of challenges. This is also an important indicator as academic tasks often require persistence and the ability to overcome obstacles. The internal locus of control indicator has the lowest mean at 3.44, but it still falls within the high descriptive level. This indicates that students generally feel that they have control over their academic outcomes, but there may be some variability in this belief among students. From the perspective of the respondents, these results suggest that junior high school students in Davao Oriental have a strong sense of academic self-efficacy, which is a positive finding. This can lead to increased motivation to learn and a greater willingness to take on academic challenges. However, it is important for educators to recognize that not all students may feel equally confident in their academic abilities and to provide support and resources to help all students develop a strong sense of self-efficacy. The overall mean for academic self-efficacy of junior high school students from

Significant Relationship Between Science Identity and Academic Self-Efficacy of Junior High School Students from Davao Oriental

students from Davao Oriental is 3.58, with a high descriptive level. This suggests that, on average, the students have a strong belief in their ability to succeed academically. Looking at the highest to lowest mean indicators, the self-regulated learning indicator has the highest mean at 3.82, indicating that students feel confident in their ability to manage their learning processes. This is an important indicator as self-regulated learning skills are key to academic success, and students who feel capable of managing their own learning are more likely to succeed.

Davao Oriental falls under a high descriptive level, indicating that students generally have confidence in their ability to succeed academically. This result is consistent with the literature that highlights the significance of academic self-efficacy in contributing to academic success. As suggested by Bandura, Freeman, and Lightsey (1999) and Schunk and Ertmer (2000), academic self-efficacy refers to the student's beliefs and attitudes toward their capabilities to achieve academic success. This means that students with high academic self-efficacy are more likely to believe in their ability to complete academic tasks successfully and learn the materials effectively. The literature also highlights that self-efficacy beliefs can improve individual performance by increasing commitment, endeavor, and perseverance (Pintrich, 2003, as cited by Hayat et al., 2020). Thus, high academic self-efficacy can benefit students in terms of their academic performance and achievement. The literature shows that academic self-efficacy has been associated with academic success in various studies (Alivernini Lucidi, 2011; Muenks et al., 2017; Stajkovic et al., 2018; Yip, 2012).

Table 3 presents the statistical results for the significant relationship between science identity and academic self-efficacy of junior high

Table 1. Descriptive Equivalents of Science Indicators

Indicator	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Science Performance	4.61	Very Extensive
Science Competence	4.61	Very Extensive
Science Recognition	4.13	Extensive
Science Interest	4.71	Very Extensive
Overall	4.51	Very Extensive

Table 2. Descriptive Equivalents of Psychological Indicators

Indicator	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Internal Locus of Control	3.44	Extensive
Competence	3.54	Extensive
Persistence	3.54	Extensive
Self-Regulated Learning	3.82	Extensive
Overall	3.58	Extensive

school students from Davao Oriental. The table provides the following information: *r* value, *p*-value, decision on H_0 at 0.05 significance level, and interpretation.

Table 3. Significant Relationship between Principal’s Leadership Practices and Kinder-Teacher’s Commitment

Variables	<i>r</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value	Interpretation	Decision
Kinder-Teacher’s Commitment	0.897	<0.000	Significant	Reject H_0

The statistical analysis conducted in this study found a significant positive relationship between science identity and academic self-efficacy of junior high school students from Davao Oriental. The correlation coefficient (*r*) value of .300 indicates a moderate positive relationship between the two variables. Moreover, the *p*-value of 0.000, which is less than the significance level of 0.05, suggests that the observed relationship is statistically significant. The rejection of the null hypothesis (H_0) indicates that there is indeed a significant relationship between science identity and academic self-

efficacy. This finding implies that students who have a stronger science identity are more likely to have higher academic self-efficacy, which is consistent with previous research on the topic. From the perspective of the junior high school students in Davao Oriental, this finding has important implications for their academic success and future career choices. Students who identify with science and feel confident in their academic abilities are more likely to engage in science-related activities, pursue science-related careers, and achieve academic success in science-related subjects. Educators and policy-

makers should consider the importance of promoting and fostering science identity and academic self-efficacy among junior high school students. This could be achieved through targeted interventions such as mentoring programs, career counseling, and opportunities for hands-on science learning. Such interventions may help students to develop a stronger sense of science identity, build their confidence in their academic abilities, and ultimately, achieve greater success in science-related fields. The findings of the present study that showed a significant positive relationship between science identity and academic self-efficacy of junior high school students from Davao Oriental are consistent with empirical evidence from previous research. Sandrone (2022) argued that science self-efficacy and science identity are essential mediators of commitment to a STEM career. The author

highlighted the importance of these factors in promoting students' long-term interest and persistence in STEM fields. Similarly, Alhadabi (2021) found that science self-efficacy had direct positive effects on science identity and science achievement, highlighting the constructive role of self-efficacy in promoting students' success in science-related areas. Therefore, the significant positive relationship between science identity and academic self-efficacy observed in this study suggests that these factors can be important predictors of students' success and engagement in STEM fields. By fostering these factors, educators and policymakers can encourage more junior high school students in Davao Oriental to pursue and persist in STEM disciplines, leading to positive outcomes in their academic and career paths.

Domain of Science Identity Significantly Influence the Academic Self-Efficacy of Junior High School Students from Davao Oriental

Table 4 presents the results of a linear regression analysis that examines the relationship between science identity significantly influencing the academic self-efficacy of junior high school students from Davao Oriental. The table features one domain of science identity that significantly influences academic efficacy. The table presents unstandardized coefficients (B), standard errors, standardized coefficients (Beta), T-values, and significance levels for each indicator. Additionally, the table highlights the de-

cision on HO2 and its interpretation. Finally, the table also includes key statistics such as the R-value, R², F-value, and P-value. The regression analysis results indicate that the domain of science identity significantly influences the academic self-efficacy of junior high school students from Davao Oriental. Among the indicators, only science recognition significantly influences academic self-efficacy, with a beta value of .431 and a p-value of 0.000. This indicates that as science recognition increases, academic self-efficacy also increases. The overall model, which includes all the indicators of science identity, explains 20.7

The R-value (0.454) suggests a moderate positive correlation between science identity and academic self-efficacy, meaning that as science identity increases, so does academic self-efficacy. This finding is consistent with previous research that has shown a positive relationship between science identity and academic self-efficacy. The present study contributes to this lit-

erature by providing evidence specific to junior high school students from Davao Oriental. It is important to note that the relationship between science identity and academic self-efficacy is not linear. This means that the increase in academic self-efficacy may not be the same for all students who have similar levels of science identity. The strength and direction of the rela-

Table 4. Domain of Science Identity Significantly Influences the Academic Self-Efficacy of Junior High School Students from Davao Oriental

Variables	Academic Self Efficacy		Unstandardized Coefficients				
	B	Std. Error	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.
Constant	2.246	.235		9.570	0.000		
Science Performance	.000	.000	-	65535.000	-		Failed to Reject H_0
Not Significant							
Science Competence	-.260	.134	-	-1.949	-		Failed to Reject H_0
Not Significant							
Science Recognition	.414	.072	.550	5.761	.000		Reject H_0
Significant							
Science Interest	-.347	.178	-.186	-1.949	.053		Reject H_0
Significant							

$R = .454$; $R^2 = .207$, F -value = 19.131; p -value = 0.000

tionship may be influenced by other factors such as gender, socio-economic status, and cultural background. Further research is needed to explore these factors and their impact on the relationship between science identity and academic self-efficacy among junior high school students from Davao Oriental. From the perspective of the junior high school students in Davao Oriental, these findings suggest that their level of recognition of science may have a positive impact on their academic self-efficacy. Therefore, it is important to develop and implement programs and interventions that promote science recognition among students, which can in turn enhance their academic self-efficacy. Moreover, it is recommended that science educators incorporate activities and strategies that can increase the students' self-awareness as well as recognition of their achievements in science to further develop their academic self-efficacy. These findings mean that as science recognition increases, academic self-efficacy also increases. This finding is consistent with previous research

that has found science recognition, such as self-efficacy, to be a strong predictor of academic achievement (Hu et al., 2022; Mao et al., 2021; Hayat et al., 2020). Additionally, these previous studies have suggested that science recognition may have a positive influence on academic self-efficacy. The concept of self-efficacy, which is a person's belief in their ability to accomplish specific tasks, has been found to be a strong predictor of academic achievement (Hu et al., 2022; Mao et al., 2021; Hayat et al., 2020). The literature suggests that self-efficacy can influence academic achievement by impacting motivation, effort, and persistence, among other factors. Similarly, the current study found that science recognition, which is a form of self-efficacy, significantly influences academic self-efficacy among junior high school students from Davao Oriental. These results highlight the importance of promoting science recognition and self-efficacy beliefs among students to enhance their academic self-efficacy and, ultimately, their academic achievement.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the summary of the findings, the conclusions based on the findings, and the recommendations generated from the findings and conclusions. The study was conducted to determine whether there is a significant relationship between science identity and academic self-efficacy of junior high school students from Davao Oriental. The study also identified the extent of the science identity of junior high school students from Davao Oriental when analyzed in terms of science performance, competence, recognition, and interest. Moreover, the extent of academic self-efficacy of junior high school students from Davao Oriental, when analyzed in terms of internal locus of control, competence, persistence, and self-regulated learning, was also identified. Aside from the main objective of finding the relationship between science identity and academic self-efficacy, this study also sought out which domain of science identity significantly influences the academic self-efficacy of junior high school students from Davao Oriental. To find the answers, the researcher surveyed junior high school students in selected schools in the Division of Davao Oriental. The researcher employed a descriptive-correlation method of research, using an adapted questionnaire as the research instrument. The statistical tools used in interpreting and analyzing the data were Mean, Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson r , and linear regression.

4.1. Findings—Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are presented: The finding that the extent of science identity among junior high school students from Davao Oriental is very high carries important implications. A strong science identity indicates that students in this region have a positive and robust identification with the field of science. This could have significant implications for their future academic and career choices. With a high level of science identity, students are more likely to pursue science-related subjects and careers, fostering a pipeline of talent in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) fields. Additionally, a strong science identity could contribute to increased motivation, self-efficacy, and academic achievement in science. It is crucial for educators, policymakers, and stakeholders to recognize and support the development of science identity among junior high school students, as it could have long-term implications for their educational and professional trajectories. By nurturing and building upon this high level of scientific identity, educational institutions, and communities can foster a culture of scientific curiosity, exploration, and achievement among students in Davao Oriental. The finding that the extent of academic self-efficacy among junior high school students from Davao Oriental was extensive carries significant implications. Extensive levels of academic self-efficacy indicate that students in this region possess strong beliefs about their ability to succeed academically. This has important implications for their educational outcomes and future prospects. Students with high academic self-efficacy are more likely to approach academic challenges with confidence, persistence, and motivation. They were better equipped to set and achieve academic goals, overcome obstacles, and perform well in their studies. Moreover, high academic self-efficacy can contribute to positive attitudes toward learning, increased engagement in academic tasks, and improved overall academic performance. It was crucial for educators and policymakers to recognize and nurture the development of academic self-efficacy among junior high school students, as it can positively impact their educational experiences and long-term success. By

providing support, encouragement, and opportunities for students to build and enhance their academic self-efficacy, educational institutions can empower students in Davao Oriental to reach their full potential and excel academically. The finding of a significant relationship between science identity and academic self-efficacy among junior high school students from Davao Oriental holds important implications. The identified relationship suggests that students who identify strongly with science are more likely to possess higher levels of academic self-efficacy. This has significant implications for their educational and career development. When students have a strong science identity, they are more likely to perceive themselves as capable of succeeding in science-related academic tasks. This, in turn, can foster a sense of confidence, motivation, and persistence in their scientific pursuits. Students with higher academic self-efficacy are more likely to set challenging goals, engage in problem-solving, and exhibit perseverance in their academic endeavors. Moreover, a strong science identity and high academic self-efficacy could contribute to positive attitudes toward science, increased interest in STEM fields, and improved science achievement. Recognizing the importance of nurturing science identity and promoting academic self-efficacy in junior high school students could help educators and policymakers design interventions and educational programs that support the development of these crucial factors. By fostering a strong science identity and enhancing academic self-efficacy, students from Davao Oriental could be better equipped to pursue scientific careers and contribute to the advancement of science and technology in their communities and beyond. The finding that science recognition was the only domain of science identity that significantly influences the academic self-efficacy of junior high school students from Davao Oriental holds important implications for educational practices and interventions. It suggests that recognizing

and valuing students' achievements and contributions in the field of science plays a critical role in shaping their academic self-efficacy beliefs. By acknowledging and highlighting students' scientific accomplishments, educators can enhance their confidence in their abilities to succeed academically. Providing opportunities for students to receive recognition and praise for their scientific achievements can motivate them to further engage in scientific activities and develop a positive attitude towards science. Additionally, educators could create an environment that promotes a sense of belonging and identity in the scientific community, fostering students' belief in their ability to excel in scientific endeavors. By emphasizing science recognition as a means to boost academic self-efficacy, educational stakeholders can contribute to the development of students' self-confidence, motivation, and persistence in scientific pursuits, ultimately supporting their academic and career success in science-related fields.

4.2. Conclusions—The conclusions of the study are as follows: The extent of the science identity of junior high school students from Davao Oriental was extensive. The extent of academic self-efficacy of junior high school students from Davao Oriental was extensive. There is a significant relationship between science identity and academic self-efficacy of junior high school students from Davao Oriental. Science recognition was the sole domain of science identity that significantly influenced the academic self-efficacy of junior high school students from Davao Oriental.

4.3. Recommendations—Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are put forward to those concerned: Department of Education Policymakers. Based on the finding of a significant relationship between science identity and academic self-efficacy of junior high school students from Davao Oriental, it is recommended that the Department of Education policymakers focus on

promoting science identity development. The department should implement programs and initiatives to foster the growth of science identity among junior high school students. These efforts include integrating hands-on and inquiry-based learning experiences into the curriculum, showcasing successful role models in the field of science, and providing opportunities for students to engage in scientific research projects or competitions. By nurturing a sense of identity as scientists, students will likely experience increased academic self-efficacy and motivation in STEM. This, in turn, can lead to improved academic performance and a higher likelihood of pursuing STEM-related careers in the future. Therefore, investing in initiatives that support science identity development is crucial for enhancing the educational outcomes and career prospects of junior high school students in Davao Oriental.

Public and Private School Administrators. Based on the findings that the extent of academic self-efficacy among junior high school students in Davao Oriental is high, it is recommended that both public and private school administrators prioritize the continuous enhancement of academic self-efficacy within their institutions. Administrators should strive to create a supportive and empowering learning environment that fosters students' belief in their intellectual abilities. This can be achieved by implementing strategies such as providing targeted academic support programs, offering mentoring or tutoring opportunities, and promoting a growth mindset among students. Administrators should also ensure that teachers receive professional development and training on effective instructional practices that encourage self-efficacy beliefs, such as providing constructive feedback, setting attainable goals, and offering opportunities for mastery experiences. By focusing on strengthening students' academic self-efficacy, public and private school administrators can contribute to improved academic performance, increased student engagement, and overall positive educational experiences for junior high school students in Davao Oriental.

Public and Private Science Teachers. Based on the findings that there is a significant relationship between science identity and academic self-efficacy among junior high school students in Davao Oriental, it is recommended that public and private science teachers play a pivotal role in nurturing and strengthening students' science identity and academic self-efficacy. Science teachers should focus on creating engaging and interactive learning experiences that promote students' sense of belonging and identification with science. They can incorporate hands-on experiments, real-world applications, and collaborative projects that allow students to explore and experience the relevance and excitement of science. Additionally, science teachers should provide regular opportunities for students to reflect on their learning, set goals, and monitor their progress. By fostering a supportive and inclusive classroom environment, science teachers can help students develop a positive science identity and enhance their belief in their abilities to succeed in science. Furthermore, professional development programs and resources should be available to science teachers to improve their pedagogical skills and deepen their understanding of promoting science identity and academic self-efficacy among their students. By empowering science teachers with effective instructional strategies, Davao Oriental can cultivate a generation of scientifically literate and confident learners.

Parents and Guardians. For parents and guardians, it is essential to actively support and encourage their children's engagement in science education. Based on the findings that the extent of science identity and academic self-efficacy is high among junior high school students in Davao Oriental, parents, and guardians can further enhance their children's experiences and outcomes in science by taking the following steps. Firstly, they should foster a positive and supportive home environment that

values and celebrates science learning. This can involve engaging in science-related discussions and providing access to educational resources such as books, documentaries, and online platforms that promote scientific inquiry. Secondly, parents and guardians can play an active role in encouraging their children's participation in science-related extracurricular activities, such as science clubs, competitions, and community events. These opportunities allow students to explore their interests, develop their skills, and build their confidence in science. Additionally, parents and guardians should communicate regularly with teachers to stay informed about their children's progress in science and provide any necessary support at home. Lastly, they should serve as role models by expressing their enthusiasm and curiosity for science, showcasing the relevance and importance of scientific knowledge and its applications in daily life. Parents and guardians can contribute to developing their children's science identity, academic self-efficacy, and overall success in science by actively supporting their children's science education journey. Public and Private Junior High School Students. Public and private junior high school students can enhance their science education by embracing curiosity and inquiry, actively participating in hands-on activities, and joining science clubs or organizations. By nurturing a sense of wonder and asking questions, students develop a genuine passion for science. Actively engaging in laboratory experiments and practical activities allows for a deeper understanding of scientific concepts and the developing of critical thinking skills. Additionally, participating in science clubs provides opportunities for collaboration, scientific projects, and competitions, further enriching students' learning experiences. By implementing these recommendations, students can maximize their engagement and achievement in science education. Future Researchers. For future researchers, there are several avenues for further exploration in science education among junior high school students. It would be beneficial to delve deeper into the factors contributing to science identity and academic self-efficacy, such as the influence of teacher-student interactions, classroom environment, and curriculum design. Understanding these factors in greater detail can inform the development of targeted interventions and instructional strategies to enhance science identity and self-efficacy among students. Investigating the long-term effects of science identity and academic self-efficacy on students' career aspirations and educational trajectories would provide valuable insights into the potential impact of these factors on future STEM-related pursuits. Exploring the effectiveness of different pedagogical approaches, including inquiry-based learning, project-based learning, and technology integration, would improve instructional practices in junior high school science classrooms. Future researchers can expand upon these findings and contribute to advancing science education by exploring these areas in greater depth.

5. References

5. References

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